

Harpephyllum affrum Wild plum

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 15 meters

Distribution:

The wild plum grows from the Eastern Cape northwards through KwaZulu-Natal, Swaziland, southern Mozambique, Limpopo and into Zimbabwe. This is a popular tree in frost-free areas.

Importance:

The tree's fruit is edible and enjoyed by birds, animals, and humans. It is used for jams, jellies, and rosé wine. The bark is a traditional medicine for acne, eczema, and "bad blood," often used in skin washes. Burnt bark treats sprains and fractures, while it also serves as a dye. In the Eastern Cape, root decoctions are used for paralysis linked to sorcery.

PromethION Sequencing Report :

Output: 20.11 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 3.17 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.45 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 96.4%, Duplicated: 2.1%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 1 454.18 kilobases

Contig number: 1 778

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